

ANALYSIS OF EXPERIMENTAL DATA ON THE CATALYTIC PROCESSING OF PYROLYSIS DISTILLATE

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Annotation: In this article discusses analysis of experimental data on the catalytic processing of pyrolysis distillate

Keywords: processing, experimental data, raw materials, hydrogenation

Rational utilization of technological wastes of gas chemical complexes into high-quality petroleum products is one of the priority areas for the further development of oil and gas processing enterprises. In accordance with the predicted increase in the volume of natural gas processing in the republic, the volume of pyrolysis distillate formed is also growing.

Given the value of this waste as an important industrial raw material, the catalytic processing of pyrolysis distillate into target products will make it possible to expand the range and increase the production of petroleum products - gasoline fractions, light naphtha and pyrolysis oil. In this aspect, the development of highly efficient processes for the deep processing of pyrolysis distillate, based on catalytic processes for the hydrotreatment of raw materials and the hydrogenation of intermediate reaction products (hydrogenate), is of great importance.

The study of the processes of hydrotreatment of pyrolysis distillate and hydrogenation of intermediate products (hydrogenate) was carried out in an experimental autoclave [1]. During the experiments, the main attention was paid to reducing the residual sulfur content in samples of raw materials and intermediate products. Determination of the residual sulfur content in raw materials, hydrogenate and distillates of the target fractions was carried out according to the accelerated method for determining sulfur by GOST 1437-75 [2].

Hydrotreatment of the pyrolysis distillate into hydrogen sulfide and hydrogenation of the hydrogenation product were carried out under rational process parameters, established according to the literature data, at a hydrogen pressure of 4–5 atm and a temperature of 300–420 °S, which are close to the operating conditions of industrial hydrotreatment units [3,4,5].

In table. Figure 1 shows the performance of the gasoline fraction isolated in an autoclave from the pyrolysis distillate hydrogenation product at a process temperature of 420 ± 5 °S, a hydrogen pressure of $3.5 \div 4.0$ MPa, in the presence of an AKM catalyst and a catalyst to feed ratio of 1:10.

Table 1

Indicators of the fraction of gasoline isolated from the hydrogenate of pyrodistillate hydrogenate in the presence of an AKM catalyst

No	The name of indicators	Pyrolysis distillate hydrogenate	Gasoline fraction (NK - 180 °S)
1	Faction content, % (gen.)	75,0	58,5
2	Density at 20 °S $\rho=420$, kg/m ³	842	832
3	Sulfur content, % (mass.)	0,098	0,011
5	Fractional composition: % (gen.), °S:		
	- initial boiling point	40	43
	10 %	57	68
	50 %	96	102
	90 %	166	169
	95 %	170	176
	- end boiling point	170	182
6	Exit, % (gen.)	96	96,5
7	Residue in the flask and losses, % (gen.)	4,0	3,5

As can be seen from Table. 1, under the given conditions of the experiment, the depth of hydroconversion of the pyrolysis distillate into fuel distillates was 75%. A distillate of gasoline fractions (i.b. - 180 °S) was obtained in the amount of 58.5%, with a sulfur content of 0.011% (mass.).

Table 2 shows the performance of gasoline and kerosene fractions isolated from the pyrolysis distillate hydrogenate at 350 °S, a hydrogen-containing gas pressure of 3.5 MPa, in the presence of an AKM catalyst and at a catalyst to feedstock ratio of 1:10.

Table 2

The results of analyzes of pyrolysis distillate and distillates of its fractions, carried out at the CPL of the Bukhara Oil Refinery

№	The name of indicators	Gasoline fractions according to OzDSt 3031:2015	pyrolysis distillate	Fraction distillates	
				gasoline	Kerosene
1	Density at 20 °S, kg/m ³	not normal.	842,5	753,6	835,2
2	Mass fraction of sulfur, ppm,	500	190	110	120
3	Fractional composition according to GOST 2177-99:				
	- initial boiling point, °S	35	45	44	47
	10 %	75	66	62	66
	50 %	120	102	97	102
	90 %	190	177	166	173
	- end boiling point, °S	215	209	178	205
4	Remainder, % (gen.)	2,0	1,5	1,5	1,5
5	Remaining and loss, % (gen.)	4,0	2,5	2,5	2,5
6	Pressure of saturated vapors of gasoline, kPa, no more	66,7	44	50,7	43,2
7	Mass content of resins, mg/100 sm ³ , no more	5	450	330	346
8	Appearance	Transparent	light brown		

As can be seen from Table. 2, the mass fraction of sulfur in the fractions of the pyrolysis distillate treated in the presence of the AKM catalyst under the above conditions decreases by 70–80 mg/kg, and the content of resins in their composition decreases by 104–120 mg/100 sm³. At the same time, the density of the obtained distillate fractions decreases by 7.3÷8.9 kg/m³, and the temperature regime of their distillation does not change significantly [6,7,8].

Thus, the results of experiments on studying the processes of hydrogenation of pyrolysis distillate in the presence of an AKM catalyst show that at 300–360 °S and a hydrogen pressure of 3.5–4.5 MPa, sulfur-containing compounds of the

raw material undergo deep transformations into the desired hydrocarbon composition. final products due to the simultaneous flow of processes of hydrogenation, splitting and hydrodesulfurization of raw materials [8].

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